

NOTES

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metals	Ionic strength	$\mu = 0.05$			$\mu = 0.10$			$\mu = 0.15$		
		I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
	$\log K_1^H$	6.95*			6.89			6.75		
		6.90**			6.80			6.80		
Cu ^{II}	$\log K_1$	6.84	6.80	7.19	6.99	—	7.08	6.58	6.52	6.82
	$\log K_2$	6.28	6.24	5.94	5.96	—	5.96	6.08	6.02	5.76
	$\log \beta_n$	18.12	18.04	18.18	12.95	—	12.99	12.66	12.54	12.58
Ni ^{II}	$\log K_1$	5.98	—	5.98	4.96	4.90	5.28	5.16	4.82	5.11
	$\log K_2$	4.62	—	4.72	4.42	4.86	4.21	3.78	3.44	3.88
	$\log \beta_n$	10.60	—	10.65	9.38	9.26	9.49	8.94	8.26	8.99

* Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values. ** Linear plot method. I = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values II = mid-point method, III = interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

The metal contents were estimated by standard methods⁵. The solution of 2N-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (DBSPT) was prepared in dioxane. The carbonate-free NaOH solution was prepared in conductivity water and used in potentiometric titrations. Stock solutions of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid were prepared in conductivity water.

A Elico Lt-10 pH meter having glass and saturated calomel electrode was used for the titrations. The pH meter was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (pH 4.05).

Results

Proton ligand stability constant : In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in the complex formation and proton is replaced from it by the metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, the number of dissociable protons, Y, attached to ligand molecule is one.

Calculation of proton ligand stability constants was carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}H$ against pH and the value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}H=0.5$. The plot of $\log(\bar{n}H/1-\bar{n}H)$ vs pH was also drawn. From this pK_2 was evaluated. This value agrees quite well with that obtained by half-integral method (Table 1).

Metal ligand stability constant : The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} systems were determined by half-integral method plotting the $\bar{n}$ values against pL. These values were further confirmed by the various computational method⁶, viz. interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, mid-point method and interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

Discussion

As the ionic strength increases the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ decrease. This observation is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel⁷ equation. The observed order of stability for the above metal

ions is Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}, and conforms to Irving-Williams⁸ order of stability.

The formation of six-membered ring complex has created a very unusual features in the compound, i.e. a six- and five-membered ring is alternate to each other predicting the high stability which has actually been observed by the experimental data. Another phenomenon observed in the ligand molecule is the appearance of conjugated double and single bond in the formation of metal chelates which is also responsible for the higher stability data.

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Synthesis of D-Glycero-D-galactoheptose

RATHINDRA NATH RAY

Research Chemist, Development Consultants Private Limited, Calcutta-700 016

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IN 1945 Sowden and Fischer¹ reacted aldoses with nitromethane in the presence of sodium methoxide to form the corresponding nitroalcohols which were then subjected to the Nef reaction². In the Nef reaction an aqueous solution of the sodium nitroalcohol is added to a moderately concentrated sulphuric acid solution when the next higher aldose is formed together with sodium bisulphate with the evolution of nitrous oxide. Using this synthesis

Sowden and Fischer prepared D-arabinose and D-ribose from D-erythrose³, and L-glucose and L-mannose from L-arabinose⁴. In this communication D-mannose was condensed with nitromethane in the presence of sodium methoxide to give 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol in high yield. The carbohydrate nitroalcohol was then subjected to the Nef reaction with 18 N sulphuric acid. As a result a pure product of D-glycero-D-galactoheptose was obtained in high yield.

Experimental

1-Nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol: In the first step, D-mannose (4 g) in absolute methanol (10 ml) and of nitromethane (16 ml) was added to sodium (1 g) in absolute methanol (18 ml). The resulting mixture was shaken for 5 h. The product was then cooled to -20° . It was filtered and the precipitate was washed first with methanol and then with ether. It was dissolved in ice-water and then passed through a cation-exchange column. The effluent was concentrated under reduced pressure when crystals of 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol separated out (2.6 g, 68%), m.p. 198° (Found: C, 35.10; H, 5.41; N, 5.82. Calcd. C, 35.14; H, 5.43; N, 5.85%); $[\alpha]_D +24^{\circ}$.

Conversion of 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol to D-glycero-D-galactoheptose: 1-Nitro-1-deoxy-D-glycero-D-galactoheptitol (0.5 g) was dissolved in 1 N sodium hydroxide (2 ml) and the mixture was then added to 18 N sulphuric acid (4 ml) with stirring. Heating facilitated the reaction. It was heated for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and passed through three ion-exchange columns. The resulting solution was concentrated when D-glycero-D-galactoheptose was obtained (0.44 g, 88%), m.p. $135-136^{\circ}$ (Found: C, 40.2, H, 6.63. Calcd. C, 40.0; H, 6.66%); $[\alpha]_D +68^{\circ}$. It was dissolved in water and then acidified with acetic acid. The solution was treated with phenylhydrazine in 50% acetic acid when D-glycero-D-galactoheptose phenylhydrazone precipitated out on standing, m.p. 196° .

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Biflavonoids from Leaves of *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f.

F. R. ANSARI, W. H. ANSARI* and W. RAHMAN
Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

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THE genus *Cunninghamia* (Family, Taxodiaceae) consists of only two species, evergreen conifers found in China, of which *Cunninghamia lanceolata*

Hook. f. (Syn. *C. sinensis* R. Br.) is grown in India as an ornamental plant. The wood is of commercial value as being used for the manufacture of paper pulp¹.

Both the species, *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f. and *C. lanceolata* Var², were examined earlier, and found to contain hinokiflavone and kayaflavone, alongwith sequoiaflavone or sotetsuflavone. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of eight flavonoid pigments from the leaf extracts of *Cunninghamia lanceolata* Hook. f. Robustaflavone is being reported for the first time in the genus *Cunninghamia* and its presence in the species may serve as a useful taxonomic marker.

The phenolic extractives of powdered leaves by solvent fractionation and column chromatography (Si-gel) followed by preparative tlc yielded five flavonoid fractions (+ve shinoda test)⁴ labelled as CLI-CLV. CLI on methylation followed by tlc examination and characteristic fluorescence in uv light^{4,6} was found to be the mixture of amentoflavone and robustaflavone. The methylated product was subjected to preparative tlc to give CLI MI and CLI MII. CLI MI, m.p. 226° , Rf 0.41, mol. wt. 622 (*M*) was characterised as amentoflavone hexamethyl ether (**1e**) by comparison with authentic sample (m.p., Rf values, fluorescence in uv light and nmr data)^{5,7,8}, CLI MII, m.p. 308° , Rf 0.51, mol. wt. 622 (*M*) was found identical with authentic sample of robustaflavone hexamethyl ether (**2b**) (m.p., Rf values, fluorescence in uv light and nmr data)^{9,6}. CLII was found on complete methylation to be a mixture of hinokiflavone and mono-*o*-methylamentoflavone on tlc (Rf values and fluorescence in uv light)⁵. CLII was, therefore, subjected to CCD separation between ethylmethyl ketone and borate buffer (pH 9.8) to give CLII X and CLII Y. CLII X was characterised as sequoiaflavone (**1b**) by nmr studies of its acetate and methyl ether and also by comparison with authentic sample⁸. CLII Y was identified with hinokiflavone (**3a**) by comparison with authentic samples (m.p., Rf values, and nmr data of acetate and methyl ether)¹⁰. CLIII and its complete methyl ether CLIII M showed on tlc examination to be mono-*o*-methylhinokiflavone. On acetylation, it gave an acetate CLIIIA, m.p. $213-214^{\circ}$, which was analysed for isocryptomerin tetraacetate by nmr spectral studies¹¹. CLIII was thus assigned the structure as isocryptomerin (**3b**). Tlc examination of CLIV and its complete methyl ether showed it to be a mixture of di-*o*-methylamentoflavone and apigenin^{5,12}. CLIV on CCD separation yielded CLIV X and CLIV Y which were characterised as I-7, II-7-di-*o*-methylamentoflavone (**1c**) and apigenin (**4a**), respectively by direct comparison of nmr data of their acetates with those of the authentic samples^{13,14}. Tlc examination of CLV and its methyl ether showed it to be tri-*o*-methylamentoflavone. It was identified as kayaflavone (**1d**) by comparison of nmr data of its acetate with that of the authentic sample¹⁵.